

NEUROLINGUISTICS: LANGUAGE AND THE BRAIN

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Neurolinguistics is a modern discipline that emerged due to the development of computer technologies and the convergence of scientific interests of neurology and linguistics. It is classified as a field of cognitive science. The focus of the new discipline has shifted from the study of language as a communication tool to the neurological reactions of the brain during communication. Here, two important aspects of research should be highlighted:

- the brain's perception of language as a means of communication, that is, the study of the influence of external factors;

- language as a product of the interaction of various areas of the brain, that is, internal conditions and factors of communication.

Neurolinguistics studies the work of the brain and its properties during speech activity, thinking, emotional perception and memory. Thus, neurolinguistics has established itself as an interdisciplinary science, which is closest to psycholinguistics. And sometimes they are considered a single science.

Neurolinguistics and psycholinguistics

Neurolinguistics is a new interdisciplinary science, so many scientists consider it a part of psycholinguistics. For example, according to the interpretation of linguist Tatyana Chernigovskaya, neurolinguistics is a part of psycholinguistics, but has a more precise description of the methodology and subject.

Neurolinguistic research has a more precise subject field of study, since a laboratory experiment shows which part of the brain is involved during the experiment. The direct interest of neurolinguistics is aimed at studying three zones of the left hemisphere responsible for the functioning of speech:

Broca's area (where oral speech control reactions occur);

Wernicke's area (responsible for perception and understanding);

occipital part (where logical and grammatical memorization occurs).

Despite the definition of zones that are responsible for our ability to communicate, they are developed differently in everyone. A clear example is the brain of a deaf-mute person - the part of the brain that should be responsible for the formation and perception of speech has lost its ability, and in its place the

property of peripheral vision, which is very well developed in deaf-mute people, has mutated.

Research stages, methods and problems of neurolinguistics

The interest of neurolinguistic research is aimed at studying the influence of language on speech mechanisms in the brain (by the way, we recommend reading the article "Language and Thinking" on this topic). Usually, these observations have three complementary stages:

Linguistic stage.

Neurophysiological stage.

Psychological stage.

In the process of producing human speech, several zones are involved in the brain - some perform the main functions, others - auxiliary. Therefore, neurolinguistic research, in addition to its own special methods, always uses the methods of related disciplines:

the observation method helps to determine speech disorders, motor skills of the speech apparatus, memory and imagination;

sodium amytal test - part of the use of X-rays, helps to study the neurological aspects of the problem;

functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) - measures blood flow in the brain during the performance of various tasks, visualization;

electrical stimulation or electroconvulsive therapy - helps to determine the area of the brain responsible for a particular reaction;

eye-tracking is used to study the reaction of the eyes during reading;

dichotomous listening – testing the perception of sound vibrations (usually performed separately on the right and left ears, which physiologically perceive sound differently);

stereotaxic method – direct penetration into the brain by surgery.

For the reliability of neurolinguistic research, scientists must turn to such sciences as neurology, psychology, psycholinguistics, neurophysiology, neuropsychology, speech therapy, neurosurgery, biophysics and biochemistry. A wide range of brain research methods shows not only the interdisciplinary status of neurolinguistics, but also states the fact of the long-term formation of this science into a separate area of knowledge.

Neuropsychological research refers to the study of both speech perception disorders and the observation of neurolinguistic processes in people without obvious deviations. This includes:

- speech pathologies;

- various speech function disorders (aphasia);
- the effect of meditation on a person's character and changes in their brain;
- research on oncological diseases of the brain;
- research on speech encoding in the hemispheres of the brain, which occurs differently in right-handed and left-handed people;
- study of the organization and system of language structure in native speakers;
- how writing (left to right and right to left) affects language perception and brain function, the formation of mental space;
- decoding of language by the brain in children;
- language functioning in the brain of adults;
- bilingualism;
- language acquisition, information processing in the brain;
- the phenomenon of hallucinations.

The interest of neurolinguistic research is also aimed at an in-depth understanding of the complexities of grammar, phonetics, speech patterns and texts in general.

Interesting facts

Discoveries in the field of neurolinguistics prove how little we know about our existence. Here are some interesting facts:

- All speech mechanisms in the brain occur in the left hemisphere. Therefore, even with a strong disruption of the right hemisphere, this does not affect speech activity in any way.
- A newborn child learns to perceive human language during the first three years of life, first distinguishing it from the general noise that surrounds him.
- Neurolinguistic research proves that language is not only an important factor in socialization, but also a tool for the formation of neural connections that are responsible for normal human development.

Thus, the latest important discovery of neurobiology is the plasticity of our brain, its ability to constantly change, regardless of age. But, at the same time, we still know very little about the phenomenon of neuroplasticity itself.

How Language Shapes Our Thinking

Psycholinguist and cognitive scientist Lera Boroditsky from the University of California, San Diego specializes in proving how languages shape our thinking. Using the results of research by ethnologists, cognitive scientists, cultural scientists, and linguists, she compares different language structures in the lab.

She is also a co-author of the theory of linguistic relativity, which proves that language determines thinking and creates certain cognitive categories, which in turn shape traditions and various non-linguistic forms of behavior.

Her main thesis is that the world's 7,000 languages create their own sound, vocabulary, and most importantly, language structure. It is the language structure that often determines how we describe events, what images arise in our brains. For example, an English-speaking and a Spanish-speaking witness to a man breaking a vase will make different accents in accordance with the grammar rules of their native language. So, it turns out that in English the emphasis falls on the subject, while in Spanish it falls on the event. That is why, when describing the same event, people will talk about it differently, make different accents. Language structures are only one of the aspects that affect the cognitive abilities of the brain.

In addition to obvious differences in grammar, languages are not as universal in the tools we learn to use. For example, in English there is not such a variety of shades of color as in Russian. Some languages do not have numbers. Or in different languages the gender of concepts will not match, and in English this is not important at all. But in the language of the Australian aborigines Tayore (Kuuk Thaayorre) there are no concepts of "right" and "left": local residents use the four cardinal directions to indicate directions, but the catch is that each speaker will use them according to their location in space, and their interlocutor must very quickly comprehend the information in relation to their own location in space.

The direction of reading from right to left and from left to right has no less impact on the formation and functioning of our brain. As studies of brain reactions show, reading affects the formation of different neural connections in our brain.

Thus, neurolinguistics is a relatively young science, the discoveries of which depend on technological progress. Despite the many studies conducted over the past few decades, we still have a very poor understanding of the principles of brain function. Let's hope that the future will provide us with more information on this topic.

